

THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN KASHADARYA DURING INDEPENDENCE (ON THE EXAMPLE OF SHURTANGAZ)

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Annotation: *Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex is one of the largest gas companies in Uzbekistan. Uzbekneftegaz is a unitary subsidiary of the national holding company. It is located in Shurtan town of Guzar district of Kashkadarya region. It occupies an area of more than 150 hectares.*

Keywords: *Shurtan, Uzbekneftegaz, Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Construction of the Shurtan GKM began in 1998. Uzbekneftegaz is one of the best projects implemented by the national holding company during the years of independence and a product of international cooperation. Launched in 2001. On August 15, 2002, the first polyethylene was obtained.

The complex includes US ABB Lummus Global, Honeywell, Germany's Fisher, Ermafa, Canada's Nova Chemicals, Italy's Renco, ABB Soimi, Japan's Mitsui, Nisho Ivai, France's Upedex ", Russia's Soyuzvneshtrans, VNIIGaz and other companies took an active part. Eximbank of the United States, Chase Manhattan Bank, Pariba of France, Kommersbank of Germany, Eximbank of Japan and Hermes Insurance Agency also participated with their investments. The technological part of the complex consists of a gas purifier, a plant for the production of polyethylene granules.

According to the project's capacity, the complex will cost 4.2 billion rubles a year. 125 thousand tons of polyethylene granules, 137 thousand tons of liquefied gas, 103 thousand tons of gas condensate, 4 thousand tons of granulated sulfur, as well as 4.2 billion tons of gas. producing natural gas (fuel) produces. In 2004, 100,000 tons of polyethylene, 85,000 tons of liquefied gas, 88,000 tons of gas condensate, 2.6 billion cubic meters of gas and 100 tons of sulfur were produced.

More than 60% of the complex's products are exported to foreign countries - Ukraine, Russia, Kazakhstan, the Baltics, Poland, Hungary, Austria, Greece, Turkey, Iran, Pakistan, China and others.

On November 11, 1996, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 395 "On the construction of the Shurtan

gas-chemical complex for the production of polyethylene products" was adopted.

On June 13, 1998, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 249 "On the establishment of the Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex Construction Department within the branding apparatus of Uzbekneftegaz Corporation" was adopted. Construction of a complex has begun in Guzar.

February 1998 Uzbekneftegaz with a consortium of ABB Lummus Global (USA), ABB Soimi (Italy), Mitsui & Co, Toyo Engineering, Nisho Iwai Corp (Japan) signed an agreement on the construction of The total cost of the project is \$ 500 million. About half of these funds will be funded by members of the international consortium.

The official opening of the complex took place on December 21, 2001. The ceremony was attended by the then President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov and high-ranking officials.

On July 30, 2002, the first polymer ethylene was obtained at the complex according to the specifications. During the design, the complex is planned to produce 140,000 tons of ethylene per year. On August 15, the first "Uzbek" polyethylene under the UzClear brand was produced. During the design, the complex is planned to produce 125,000 tons of polyethylene per year.

In September 2004, he was awarded the Product Quality Award in the United States and the Medal for Product Quality and Excellence in Business in Geneva, Switzerland.

In 2005, the Lochin children's health camp was opened in the village of Miraki, Shahrhisabz district. The children of oil and gas workers have a rest at the camp. This year, with the help of the certification organization TUV CERT (Germany), the company introduced a quality management system in accordance with the requirements of the international standard ISO 9001: 2000 and received a certificate.

In 2006, Erkatoy kindergarten and 844-seat school were built in Nuristan town of Nishan district at the expense of Shurtan GKM. On July 10, by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-406 "On reorganization of the state enterprise Karshitermoplast", the enterprise "Karshitermoplast" was transferred to the balance of the complex and has a diameter of 25 mm and 250 mm. The production of polyethylene pipes was started.

In December 2007, the production of polyethylene pipe fittings was launched at Karshitermoplast.

In 2008, a system of occupational safety and health meeting the requirements of international standards was introduced in accordance with OHSAS 18001 occupational health and safety management system.

In July 2009, a line for the production of drip irrigation system components for farms in water-scarce areas was launched.

In 2010, a subsidiary of Shurtan GKM "Polyethylene Pipes" was established in Navoi FEZ. In May, the range of polyethylene pipes was 315 mm. and 630 mm. expanded by launching an extrusion line for the production of polyethylene pipes with a diameter of up to In April, a line for the production of aluminum composite panels for the front of buildings was launched.

In 2011, a workshop for the production of pasta and biscuits, as well as energy-saving lamps (all three are located separately) was opened in Dehkanabad district.

In 2012, a poultry factory was opened on the subsidiary farm ShGKM.

In 2015, the Complex was reorganized into a Unitary Subsidiary Company (USC) in the form of a Limited Liability Company (LLC). The project "Production of polymer paint" was implemented in the Karshitermoplast shop under "Shurtan GKM" LLC.

In 2017, the project "Production of polypropylene pipes based on glass fiber" was launched on the basis of "Polypropylene Pipes" in Navoi SEZ.

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